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Appendix 1
NESCent Year 4 Awards
December 1, 2007 - November 30, 2008

Name	Institution	Project Title	Start Date
Postdocs			
Josh Auld	Univ of Pittsburgh	Evaluating the effects of inbreeding on dispersal	Oct 1, 2009 (after NESCent-related fellowship in Montpellier, France)
Carlos Botero	Cornell Univ	Evolution of conventional signals: From individuals to populations and back	January 2009
Marc Lajeunesse	Cornell Univ	Meta-analysis and the comparative phylogenetic method	October 2008
Trina Roberts	Univ of Alaska, Fairbanks	Sticky tips and misplaced roots: Is there a bias in intraspecific phylogenetics?	August 2008
Stephen Smith	Yale Univ	Integrating species distribution modeling and phylogenetics	October 2008
Sabbatical Scholars			
Michael Antolin	Colorado State Univ	Sabbatical book project: Genetics of small populations	3 6-wk visits: Sept 15-Oct 30, 2008; Jan 15-Feb 28, 2009; April 1-May 15, 2009
Stephen "Christian" d'Orgeix	Virginia State Univ	Evolution courses, mountaintop lizards and a view toward the future research	Sept 08-May 09
Elizabeth Lacey	University of NC, Greensboro	Temperature and the evolution of floral design	Aug-Dec 08
Robert Pennock	Michigan State Univ	Darwinian design: From artificial life to evolving intelligence	Mar-Aug 08
Triangle Visiting Scholars			
Marcy Uyenoyama	Duke Univ	Sampling-based methods for association mapping	Jan-May 2008
Brian Wiegmann	NC State University	Phylogenetic relationships in the order Diptera primarily from DNA sequence data	Jan-May 2008
Short-Term Scholars			
Michael Alfaro, Luke Harmon, Gene Hunt	Washington State Univ, Univ of Idaho, Smithsonian Institution	Integrating fossil and molecular data in the study of diversification	Fall 2008

Name	Institution	Project Title	Start Date
Tal Dagan	Univ of Düsseldorf	The frequency and evolution of lateral gene transfer by DNA repair mechanisms	June 2008
Oliver Eulenstein	Iowa State Univ	Gene tree parsimony for genome-scale studies	May-June 2008
Jessica Gurevitch, Gordon Fox, Inderjit, Max Taub, Glenda Wardle	Stony Brook Univ, Univ of South Florida, Univ of Delhi, Univ of Sydney, Southwestern Univ	Toward a general theory of biological invasions	Jan 2009
David Houle	Florida State Univ	Measurement theory and evolutionary rates	Nov-Dec 2008
Enrico Pontelli, Brandon Chisham, Francisco Prosdocimi, Arlin Stoltzfus, Julie Thompson	New Mexico State Univ, New Mexico State Univ, Univ of Strasbourg, NIST, Univ of Strasbourg	Comparative data analysis ontology (CDAO)	Mar 2008
Working Groups			
Charles Fenster, Scott Armbruster, Pamela Diggle	Univ of Maryland; Univ of Alaska, Fairbanks; Univ of Colorado	Floral assembly: Quantifying the composition of a complex adaptive structure	Jan 2009
Scott Hodges, Elena Kramer, Hopi Hoekstra	Univ of California, Santa Barbara; Harvard Univ; Harvard Univ	Building tools for emerging model systems in Development, Evolution, and Ecology	Nov 2008
David Pfennig, Armin Moczek	Univ of NC at Chapel Hill, Indiana Univ	Evolution and development of polyphenisms: Pathways to innovation and diversification	Spring 2009
Christine Wall, Susan Williams, Rebecca German, Chris Vinyard	Duke Univ, Ohio Univ, Johns Hopkins Univ, Medical College of Ohio	Analysis and synthesis of physiologic data from the mammalian feeding apparatus	Feb 2009
Catalysis Meetings			
Cynthia Beall, Peter Robbins	Case Western Reserve Univ, Oxford Univ	Human evolution and adaptation to high- altitude hypoxia	TBD
Erika Edwards, Colin Osborne, Caroline Stromberg	Brown University, University of Sheffield, University of Washington	Toward a new synthesis of the evolutionary history and ecology of C4 grasses	TBD
Christina Richards, Oliver Bossdorf, Massimo Pigliucci	New York Univ, Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research, Stony Brook Univ	What role, if any, does heritable epigenetic variation play in phenotypic evolution?	Feb 2009
Jack Sites, Daniel Faith	Brigham Young Univ, Australian Museum	Perspectives on the origin and conservation of biodiversity in Patagonia	June 2008

Appendix 2			
Postdoctoral Fellows, Sabbatical Scholars, and Other Scientists at the Center in Year 4			
Name	Institution	Project	Starting Dates
Postdoctoral Fellows			
Gordon Burleigh	Univ of California - Davis	A Phylogenetic Database for Comparative Biology in Land Plants	Nov 2006
Kirsten Fisher	Univ of California - Berkeley	The Phylogenomics of Desiccation Tolerance in the Land Plants	Sept 2005
Ganeshkumar Ganapathy	Univ of Texas - Austin	New DCM Methods for ML, and Pattern Identification in Biogeography	Dec 2006
Einat Hazkani-Covo	Tel-Aviv University	Numt Variation in Metazoan Genomes: Gain, Loss, Duplication and Possible Function	March 2006
David Kidd	Univ of St. Andrews, UK	Phylogeographical Information Science: Linking Phylogenies and Earth History	Oct 2005
Marc Lajeunesse	Cornell Univ	Meta-analysis and the Comparative Phylogenetic Method	Oct 2008
Lauren W. McCall	Univ Cambridge	Building a Framework for the Study of Cultural Evolution	Jan 2007
Brian O'Meara	Univ of California, Davis	Methods to Examine Trait Evolution in Trees: Advancing the Field	Nov 2007
Samantha Price	Univ of Virginia	Cetartiodactyl Evolution: Understanding the Evolutionary Transition from the Terrestrial to the Aquatic Biome	Nov 2005
Brian Sidlauskas	Univ Chicago	Understanding Parallel Morphological Diversification in Sister Fish Faunas	Sept 2006
Stephen Smith	Yale Univ	Integrating Species Distribution Modeling and Phylogenetics	Oct 2008
Paula Spaeth	Stanford Univ	Competition and Meso-evolutionary Change in the Mammalian Fossil Record	Dec 2007
Amy Zanne	Masaryk Univ, Brno, Czech Rep	Hydraulic Efficiency and Safety: Do Tradeoffs have an Evolutionary Basis in the Rosids?	Aug 2006 w/NSF postdoc fellowship; NESCent postdoc begins May 2007.
Derrick Zwickl	Univ of Texas, Austin	Implementation of a Wide Range of Codon and Amino Acid Models in Bayesian Phylogenetic Software	Jan 2006
Sabbatical Scholars			
George Gilchrist	College of William and Mary	Evolution of Performance Curves in Seasonal Environments	Aug 08-June09
Michael Antolin	Colorado State Univ	Sabbatical book project: Genetics of Small Populations	3 6-wk visits: Sept 15-Oct 30, 2008; Jan 15-Feb 28, 2009; April 1-May 15, 2009
S. Christian d'Orgeix	Virginia State Univ	Evolution Courses, Mountaintop Lizards and a View Toward the Future Research	Sept 08-May 09

Postdoctoral Fellows, Sabbatical Scholars, and Other Scientists			
at the Center in Year 4			
Name	Institution	Project	Starting Dates
Elizabeth Lacey	University of NC, Greensboro	Temperature and the Evolution of Floral Design	Aug-Dec 08
Robert Pennock	Michigan State Univ	Darwinian Design: From Artificial Life to Evolving Intelligence	Mar-Aug 08
Malcolm Schug	Univ of North Carolina at Greensboro	The Role of Crossing-over and Recombination in Adaptive Evolution	9-mos, Sept 2007 - May 2008
Senior Research Scientist			
David Swofford	Joint Duke position w/ Inst for Genome Sci & Policy	PAUP, Phylogenetics, Computational Biology	Oct 2007
Short-Term Visitors			
Tal Dagan	Univ of Düsseldorf	The Frequency and Evolution of Lateral Gene Transfer by DNA Repair Mechanisms	June 2008
Oliver Eulenstein	Iowa State Univ	Gene Tree Parsimony for Genome-scale Studies	May-June 2008
Andrew Hipp, Alexander Platt	The Morton Arboretum, University of Southern California	Estimating the Probability of Continuous Character Transitions on Trees	Feb-Mar 2008
David Houle	Florida State Univ	Measurement Theory and Evolutionary Rates	Nov-Dec 2008
Enrico Pontelli, Brandon Chisham, Francisco Prosdocimi, Arlin Stoltzfus, Julie Thompson	New Mexico State Univ, New Mexico State Univ, Univ of Strasbourg, NIST, Univ of Strasbourg	Comparative Data Analysis Ontology (CDAO)	Mar 2008
Visiting Scholars/Speakers			
Katy Borner	Indiana Univ	"Studying and Communicating the Structure and Evolution of Science"	Feb 2008
Alex Dornburg	Yale Univ	Fish Fin Diversification	Aug 2008
Dan Graur	Univ of Houston	"Garbage In, Garbage Out: Effects of Sequencing and Alignment Errors on Evolutionary Inferences."	July 2008
Jotun Hein	Oxford Univ	Statistical Alignment and Footprinting	Aug 2008
Samantha Hopkins	Univ of Oregon	The Evolution of Mammalian Fossoriality	Aug 2008
Josh Roseau	National Ctr for Science Education	"Talking About Creationism with the Press and Public"	Jan 2008
Jijung Tang	Univ of South Carolina	Phylogenetic Inference and Comparative Mapping When Gene Trees and Species Trees are not Identical	July & Sept 2008
Suja Thomas	Univ of South Carolina	Phylogenetic Inference and Comparative Mapping When Gene Trees and Species Trees are not Identical	Sept 2008

Postdoctoral Fellows, Sabbatical Scholars, and Other Scientists at the Center in Year 4			
Name	Institution	Project	Starting Dates
Nicole Washington	Lawrence Berkeley Natl Labs	"Promise and Peril of Phenotype Annotation Using Ontologies to Link Human Diseases to Animal Models"	Jan 2008
David Sloan Wilson	Binghamton Univ	"The EvoS Consortium: A New Movement in Higher Education"	Sept 2008
Yitin Yang	Univ of South Carolina	Phylogenetic Inference and Comparative Mapping When Gene Trees and Species Trees are not Identical	July 2008
Local Scientists at the Center in Year 4			
<u>Visiting Scholars without NESCent Funding</u>			
Clara B. Jones	Fayetteville State Univ	Solving the Alouatta Paradox: From Polygyny to Polygynandry	April 2006-March 2008
Robert K. Peet	University of NC, Chapel Hill	Application of Taxon Concepts in Biodiversity Informatics	July 08-Aug 09
V. Louise Roth	Duke Univ	Squirrels as Models in Macroevolution; Scaling	Jan-Dec 2007
<u>Triangle Sabbatical Scholars</u>			
David Pfennig	Univ of North Carolina -- Chapel Hill	Phenotypic Plasticity and the Origins of Diversity	Sept-Dec 2007
Marcy Uyenoyama	Duke Univ	Sampling-based Methods for Association Mapping	Jan-May 2008
Brian Wiegmann	NC State Univ	Phylogenetic Relationships in the Order Diptera Primarily From DNA Sequence Data	Jan-May 2008
<u>At-Large Members of the Operations Committee</u>			
Julia Clarke	North Carolina St Univ	N/A	Sept 2007-Dec 2008
Patricia Gensel	Univ of North Carolina -- Chapel Hill	N/A	Jan 2006-Dec 2008
Greg Wray	Duke Univ	N/A	July 2006-Dec 2008

Appendix 3**NESCent Seminar Series
Year 4**

Date	Speaker	Institution	Title
Jan-11-2008	Paula Spaeth	NESCent Postdoctoral Fellow	Competition and Coexistence in North American <i>Microtus</i>
Jan-18-2008	Josh Rosenau	Public Information Project Director, National Center for Science Education	Talking to the Media About Evolution and Creationism
Feb-1-2008	Brian Sidlauskas	NESCent Postdoctoral Fellow	The Results of a Replicate Radiation: Reconstructing Parallel Ecomorphological Diversification in African and South American Characiform Fishes
Feb-15-2008	Ganesh Ganapathy	NESCent Postdoctoral Fellow	A Sample-Based Approach for Species Diversification Rates
Feb-22-2008	Todd Vision	UNC at Chapel Hill and NESCent Associate Director of Informatics	Dryad: A Digital Repository for Published Data
Feb-29-2008	Katy Borner	Department of Library Science, Indiana University	Studying and Communicating the Structure and Evolution of Science
Mar -5-2008	Alexander Platt and Andrew Hipp	The Morton Arboretum; Univ of Southern California	Estimating the Probability of Continuous Character Transitions on Trees
Mar-7-2008	Jory Weintraub	NESCent Education & Outreach	Postdoc Professional Development Round-Table Discussion on Grant Strategies
Mar-14-2008	Joel Kingsolver	UNC at Chapel Hill and NESCent Assoc. Director of Science & Synthesis	Evobeaker: Educational Software for Evolution
Mar-21-2008	Greg Wray	Dept. of Biology, Duke University and Director, IGSP Center for Evolutionary Genomics	Ganglia, Guts, and Gonads: the Genetics of Adaptations that Distinguish Us as a Species
Mar-28-2008	David Swofford	Senior Research Scientist, NESCent and Duke IGSP	The 'Ultra-Common Mechanism' Model and Other Explorations into the Relationship between Parsimony and Model-Based Approaches to Phylogenetic Inference

Date	Speaker	Institution	Title
Apr-4-2008	Rob Pennock	Michigan State University and NESCent Sabbatical Scholar	Learning Evolution and the Nature of Science Using Digital Organisms
Apr-11-2008	Brian Wiegmann	NC State Univ., and NESCent Assoc. Director of Education and Outreach	Finding Flytree: Multiple Genomic Solutions to Resolving Insect Phylogeny
Apr-18-2008	Lauren McCall	NESCent Postdoctoral Fellow	When Change is Not Evolution: The Case of Human Culture
Apr-25-2008	Julia Clarke	Dept. of Marine, Earth and Atmospheric Sciences, NC State University and NESCent	Mosaicism, Modules, and the Evolution of Birds: New Data from a Bayesian Phylogenetic Approach to the Study of Morphological Evolution
May-9-2008	Jory Weintraub	NESCent Education and Outreach	Postdoc Professional Development Activity: Developing Broader Impact Projects and Ideas for your Grant Proposals
May-16-2008	Jim Balhoff	Research Programmer, NESCent Informatics	Worlds Colliding: Approaches to Problems at the Intersection of Evolution and Ontology
May-23-2008	Hilmar Lapp	NESCent Assistant Director of Informatics	Incubating Cyberinfrastructure: Community Building and Open Collaborative Software Development at the Transition Between Mostly-Off and Always-On
Jun-6-2008	Einat Hazkani-Covo and David Kidd	NESCent Postdoctoral Fellows	Continued Discussion of Synthesis at NESCent
Jun-17-2008	Tal Dagan	Department of Botany, Heinrich-Heine University Dusseldorf, Germany	Modular Networks and Cumulative Impact of Lateral Transfer in Prokaryote Genome Evolution
Jul-15-2008	Dan Graur	University of Houston	Garbage in, Garbage Out: Effects of Sequencing and Alignment Errors on Evolutionary Inferences
Aug-4-2008	Jotun Hein	Professor of Bioinformatics, Oxford University	Statistical Alignment and Footprinting
Aug-29-2008	Craig McClain	Monterey Bay Aquarium Research Institute	Do Giants Or Miniatures Rule the Earth? Linking Biodiversity and Body Size Across the Animal Kingdom

Date	Speaker	Institution	Title
Sept-2-2008	Mark Jensen	Fortinbras Research	Catching the Greased Pig: HIV Genetic Diversity and Vaccine Design
Sept-4-2008	Terri Williams	Yale University, Dept. of Ecology and Evolutionary Biology	Crustacean Development and Evolution: a History of Repeated Parts
Sept-5-2008	Amy Grunden	North Carolina State University, Department of Microbiology	A Synthetic Biology Approach for Redesigning Organisms to Survive Environmental Stress
Sept-10-2008	David Sloan Wilson	Binghamton University, Department of Biological Studies	The EvoS Consortium: A New Movement in Higher Education
Sept-19-2008	Trina Roberts	NESCent Postdoctoral Fellow	A Tale of Two Treeshrews (or Maybe More): Systematics and Biogeography in an Obscure Mammalian Family
Sept-26-2008	Mike Antolin	Colorado State University, Dept. of Biology and NESCent Sabbatical Scholar	"Unpacking β : Within-host Dynamics and the Evolutionary Ecology of Pathogen Transmission"
Oct-3-2008	Samantha Price	NESCent Postdoctoral Fellow	Evolution of Mammalian Diets: A Tale of a NESCent Collaboration
Oct-10-2008	George Gilchrist	College of William and Mary, Dept. of Biology and NESCent Sabbatical Scholar	Adaptation to a Changing World: Lessons from Some Little Flies
Oct-17-2008	Elizabeth Lacey	UNC Greensboro, Dept. of Biology and NESCent Sabbatical Scholar	Floral Reflectance and Reproductive Thermoregulation in <i>Plantago lanceolata</i> : A Test of Adaptive Phenotypic Plasticity in Temporally Fluctuating Environments
Oct-24-2008	Jory Weintraub	NESCent Education and Outreach	Postdoc Professional Development
Oct-31-2008	Stephen Smith	NESCent Postdoctoral Fellow	TBA
Nov-7-2008	Marc Lajeunesse	NESCent Postdoctoral Fellow	TBA
Nov-21-2008	Brian O'Meara	NESCent Postdoctoral Fellow	TBA

Appendix 4			
Current Positions of Postdoctoral Fellows Completing NESCent Funding Years 1-4			
Name	Appointment	Current Employment	Starting Date
Burleigh, Gordon	Assistant Professor	Department of Botany, University of Florida at Gainesville	August 15, 2008
Fisher, Kirsten	Assistant Professor	Department of Biological Sciences, California State University at Los Angeles	September 1, 2008
Granek, Joshua	Postdoctoral Research Fellow	Department of Biology, Duke University	August 1, 2007
Hereford, Joe	NSF Minority Postdoctoral Fellow	Department of Biology, University of Maryland, College Park	January 1, 2007
Hoeksema, Jason	Assistant Professor	Department of Biology, University of Mississippi	August 1, 2007
Hopkins, Samantha	Assistant Professor	Clark Honors College, University of Oregon	September 1, 2007
Kidd, David	Postdoctoral Research Fellow	Centre for Population Biology, Imperial College London, United Kingdom	September 1, 2008
Price, Samantha	Postdoctoral Research Fellow	Department of Evolution and Ecology, University of California, Davis	November 1, 2008
Zanne, Amy	Assistant Professor	Department of Biology, University of Missouri, St Louis	August 1, 2008
Zwickl, Derrick	Postdoctoral Research Fellow	Department of Ecology and Evolutionary Biology, University of Kansas	May 1, 2008

Appendix 5				
Meetings Held at NESCent				
Year 4 December 1, 2007 - November 30, 2008				
Meeting Dates	Group Leader(s)	Topic	Type	Actual Attendees
December 5 - 7, 2007	Gould, Fred Sinkins, Steven Hartl, Daniel	Selfish DNA and the Genetic Control of Vector-Borne Diseases	Catalysis	32
December 10 - 14, 2007	Lapp, Hilmar	Hackathon on Comparative Methods in R	Informatics	29
January 10 - 15, 2008	Alberts, Susan Strier, Karen	Evolutionary Ecology of Primate Life Histories	Work Group	10
January 17 - 18, 2008	Uyenoyama, Marcy Tokuta, Alade Nielsen, Rasmus	Genomic Patterns and Processes of Introgression	Triangle Work Group	20
January 17 - 18, 2008	Waller, Don	Society for the Study of Evolution	Hosted	13
January 18, 2008	Stone, Don	From Beta Taxonomy to DNA Barcoding	Hosted	9
February 1 - 2, 2008	Nunn, Charles Hare, Brian	How Does Cognition Evolve?	Work Group	16
February 6 - 7, 2008	Kingsolver, Joel	NESCent Scientific Advisory Board	Advisory	13
February 28 - March 1, 2008	Magwene, Paul Houle, David	Modeling Variation in Gene Networks	Work Group	10
March 19 - 21, 2008	NSF	National Science Foundation Site Visit	Hosted	10
April 8 - 10, 2008	Forde, Samantha Gudelj, Ivana	Mathematical Models, Microbes & Evolutionary Diversification	Work Group	12
April 17 - 21, 2008	Mabee, Paula Vision, Todd	Phenoscape Core Meeting and Data Jamboree	Hosted	14
April 21 - 25, 2008	Buckley, Lauren Angilletta, Michael Holt, Robert Tewksbury, Joshua	NESCent-NCEAS Mechanistic Distribution Models: Energetics, Fitness, & Population Dynamics	Work Group	17

Meetings Held at NESCent				
Year 4 December 1, 2007 - November 30, 2008				
Meeting Dates	Group Leader(s)	Topic	Type	Actual Attendees
April 25 - 28, 2008	Payne, Jonathan Stempien, Jennifer Kowalewski, Michael	Phanerozoic Body Size Trends in Time and Space: Macroevolution and Macroecology	Work Group	11
May 1 - 3, 2008	Donovan, Sam	EOG TREE	Work Group	9
May 1 - 3, 2008	Lahti, David	Relaxed Selection and Trait Loss in Evolution	Work Group	12
May 5 - 8, 2008	Clarke, Julia Nagalingum, Nathalie Wiegmann, Brian	Clockwork: Redefining Interfaces for Molecular Biology and Paleontology	Triangle Work Group	43
May 13 - 14, 2008	Hanken, Jim Moritz, Craig Wake, David	Vertebrate Network Meeting	Co-Sponsored	28
May 15 - 16, 2008	Govindaraju, Diddahally Clark, Andrew Mackay, Trudy Stearns, Stephen	Measuring Evolutionary Change in Modern Human Populations	Work Group	10
May 19 - 22, 2008	Stoltzfus, Arlin Vos, Rutger	Evolutionary Informatics: Supporting Interoperability in Evolutionary Analysis	Work Group	11
May 21 - 23, 2008	Uno, Gordon Scotchmoor, Judy	Evolution Across the Curriculum	Work Group	17
May 27 - 30, 2008	Graham, Catherine Kozak, Ken Rabhbek, Carsten	Montane Biodiversity	Work Group	14
May 28 - 30, 2008	Jungck, John Weosstein, Anton E.	Synergistic Evolutionary LEarning Consortium: Evolution in AcTION	Work Group	13
May 29, 2008	Jungck, John Weosstein, Anton E.	Synergistic Evolutionary LEarning Consortium Workshop	Workshop	25
June 9 - 12, 2008	Cracraft, Joel Siddall, Mark	Developing an Integrative Algorithmic Method for Historical Biogeography	Work Group	15

Meetings Held at NESCent				
Year 4 December 1, 2007 - November 30, 2008				
Meeting Dates	Group Leader(s)	Topic	Type	Actual Attendees
June 16 - 19, 2008	Sites, Jack Faith, Daniel	Perspectives on the Origin & Conservation of Biodiversity in Patagonia (& PIRE)	Catalysis	35
June 23 - 25, 2008	Peet, Robert	Toward an International Exchange Standard on Vegetation and Biodiversity Co-occurrence Data	Hosted	4
July 11 - 13, 2008	Clements, David	GMOD Workshop	Hosted	30
July 14 - 18, 2008	Fail, Joseph	Teaching An Elementary Story of Life	Education	12
July 24 - August 4, 2008	Lapp, Hilmar	Phyloinformatics Summer Course	Education	53
August 22 - 25, 2008	Alberts, Susan Strier, Karen	Evolutionary Ecology of Primate Life Histories	Work Group	9
September 11 - 12, 2008	Smith, Kathleen	NESCent Summit	Advisory	41
September 12 - 13, 2008	Smith, Kathleen	NESCent Senior Advisory Board	Advisory	9
October 2 - 4, 2008	Forde, Samantha Gudelj, Ivana	Mathematical Models, Microbes & Evolutionary Diversification	Work Group	13
October 9 - 12, 2008	Magwene, Paul Houle, David	Modeling Variation in Gene Networks	Work Group	10
October 26 - 30, 2008	Donoghue, Michael Manos, Paul	Phytogeography of the Northern Hemisphere	Work Group	15
October 28 - 30, 2008	Allendorf, Fred Schwartz, Michael	Genetic Monitoring (GeM) Working Group	Work Group	19

Appendix 6
Year 4 Participants Lists – NESCent Sponsored Meetings
December 1, 2007 - November 30, 2008

Catalysis Meetings

December 5-7, 2007

Selfish DNA and the genetic control of vector-borne diseases

Coordinators: Fred Gould, Steven Sinkins, Daniel Hartl

Participants:

Austin Burt	Imperial College
Dana Carroll	University of Utah
Steve Dobson	University of Kentucky
Paul Eggleston	Keele University
Bill Engels	University of Wisconsin
Mac Fraser	University of Notre Dame
Charles Godfray	Oxford University
Kent Golic	University of Utah
Fred Gould	North Carolina State University
Al Handler	University of Florida
Dan Hartl	Harvard University
Bruce Hay	California Institute of Technology
Yunxin Huang	North Carolina State University
Marcelo Jacobs-Lorena	Johns Hopkins University
Joel Kingsolver	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Mathieu Legros	North Carolina State University
Alun Lloyd	North Carolina State University
Marce Lorenzen	Kansas State University
John Marshall	University of California - Los Angeles
Mohamed Noor	Duke University
Ken Olson	Colorado State University
Fernando Pardo-Manuel de Villena	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Alex Perkins	University of California - Davis
Jason Rasgon	Johns Hopkins University
Mark Rausher	Duke University
Guy Reeves	University of Perugia
Steve Sinkins	Oxford University
Shannon Takala	University of Maryland
Yun Tao	Emory University
Michael Turrelli	University of California - Davis

Mike Wade
Catherine Ward

University of Indiana
California Institute of Technology

June 16 - 19, 2008

**Perspectives on the Origin and Conservation of
Biodiversity in Patagonia**

Coordinators: Jack Sites and Daniel Faith

Participants:

Daniel Ariztegui

Université de Genève

Carlos Baeza

Universidad de Concepcion

Bryan Carstens

Louisiana State University - Baton Rouge

Jeannine Cavender-Bares

University of Minnesota

Andrea Coccuci

Universidad de Cordoba

Keith Crandall

Brigham Young University

Victor Cussac

Universidad de Comahue

Dan Faith

The Australian Museum

Simon Ferrier

Commonwealth Scientific & Industrial Research Organization

Catherine Graham

Stony Brook University

Evelyn Habit

Universidad de Concepcion

Michael Hickerson

Queens College

Carlos Jara

Universidad Austral de Chile

Jerry Johnson

Brigham Young University

Leigh Johnson

Brigham Young University

Jeremy Kerr

University of Ottawa

David Kidd

NESCent

Pablo Marquet

Universidad Catolica de Chile

Christy McCain

University of Colorado - Boulder

Brian McGill

University of Arizona

Jim McGuire

University of California - Berkeley

Mariana Morando

Centro Nacional Patagonico

Partricio Moreno

Universidad de Chile

José Nuñez

Universidad Austral de Chile

Guillermo Ortí

University of Nebraska

Raúl Poznar

Darwinion Botanical Institute

Jorge Rabassa

Universidad Nacional de la Patagonia Ushuaia

Leslie Rissler

University of Alabama

Daniel Ruzzante

Dalhousie University

Alicia Sérsic

Universidad de Cordoba

Christine Simon

University of Connecticut

Jack W. Sites, Jr.

Brigham Young University

Pedro Victoriano

Universidad de Concepcion

Sandra Walde
Jonathan Waters

Dalhousie University
University of Otago

Working Group Meetings

January 10 - 15, 2008

Participants:

Diane Brockman
Anne Bronikowski
Marina Cords
Linda Fedigan
Bill Morris
Anne Pusey
Tara Stoinski
Karen Strier
Jun Yang

Evolutionary Ecology of Primate Life Histories Coordinators: Susan Alberts and Karen Strier

University of North Carolina - Charlotte
Iowa State University
Columbia University
University of Calgary
Duke University
University of Minnesota
Zoo Atlanta and Dian Fossey Gorilla Fund
University of Wisconsin
Duke University

February 1 - 2, 2008

Participants

Filippo Aureli
Elizabeth Brannon
Christine Drea
Brian Hare
Daniel Haun
Marc Hauser
Esther Herrmann
Lucy Jacobs
Evan MacLean
Charlie Nunn
Michael Platt
Alex Rosati
Amanda Seed
Michael Tomasello
Carel van Schaik
Victoria Wobber

How Does Cognition Evolve? Coordinators: Charles Nunn and Brian Hare

Liverpool John Moores University
Duke University
Duke University
Duke University
Max Planck Institute
Harvard University
Max Planck Institute
University of California - Berkeley
Duke University
University of California - Berkeley
Duke University
Duke University
Max Planck Institute
Max Planck Institute
University of Zurich
Harvard University

February 28 - March 1, 2008

Participants

David Houle
Hao Li
Paul Magwene
Jason Mezey
Jason Moore
Patrick Phillips
Matt Rockman
Mark Siegal
Joshua Socolar
Patricia Wittkopp

Modeling Variation in Gene Networks

Coordinators: Paul Magwene and David Houle

Florida State University
University of California – San Francisco
Duke University
Cornell University
Dartmouth College
University of Oregon
Princeton University
New York University
Duke University
University of Michigan

April 8-10, 2008

Participants

Robert Beardmore
Christina Burch
Michael Doebeli
Tom Ferenci
Samantha Forde
Ivana Gudelj
Christopher Marx
Justin Meyer
Konstantin Mischaikow
Olin Silander
Hal Smith
Joshua Weitz

Mathematical Models, Microbes & Evolutionary Diversification

Coordinators: Samantha Forde and Ivana Gudelj

Imperial College
University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
University of British Columbia
University of Sidney
University of California - Santa Cruz
University of Bath
Harvard University
Michigan State University
Rutgers University
Swiss Federal Institute of Technology - Zurich
Arizona State University
Georgia Institute of Technology

April 21 - 25, 2008

Participants

Amy Angert
Michael Angilletta
Lauren Buckley

NESCent-NCEAS Mechanistic Distribution Models: Energetics, Fitness, & Population Dynamics

Coordinators: Lauren Buckley, Michael Angilletta, Robert Holt, and Joshua Tewksbury

Colorado State University
Indiana State University
University of California - Santa Barbara

Amanda Chunco	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Lisa Crozier	NOAA Fisheries
George Gilchrist	College of William and Mary
Sarah Gilman	The Claremont Colleges
Robert Holt	University of Florida
Timothy Keitt	University of Texas - Austin
Joel Kingsolver	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Sean Menke	North Carolina State University
Warren Porter	University of Wisconsin - Madison
Leslie Rissler	University of Alabama
Michael Sears	Southern Illinois University
Kimberly Sheldon	University of Washington
Joshua Tewksbury	University of Washington
Mark Urban	University of California - Santa Barbara

April 25 - 28, 2008

**Phanerozoic Body Size Trends in Time & Space:
Macroevolution & Macroecology**

**Coordinators: Jonathan Payne, Jennifer Stempien and
Michael Kowalewski**

Participants

Alison Boyer	University of New Mexico
Seth Finnegan	Stanford University
Michal Kowalewski	Virginia Polytechnic Institute
Richard Krause	Berlin Museum of Natural History
Craig McClain	Monterey Bay Aquarium Research Institute
Daniel McShea	Duke University
Philip Novack-Gottshall	University of West Georgia
Jonathan Payne	Stanford University
Felisa Smith	University of New Mexico
Jennifer Stempien	University of Colorado
Steve Wang	Swarthmore College

May 1 - 3, 2008

EOG TREE

Coordinator: Sam Donovan

Participants

David Baum	University of Wisconsin - Madison
Paul Beardsley	Biological Sciences Curriculum Study
Sam Donovan	University of Pittsburgh
Kristy Havlerson	University of Missouri

Bill Hoese
 Erin Naegle
 John Paul
 Chris Pires
 Jim Smith

California State University - Fullerton
 Idaho State University
 University of Pittsburgh
 University of Missouri
 Michigan State University

May 1 - 3, 2008

Relaxed Selection and Trait Loss in Evolution

Coordinator: David Lahti

Participants

Beverly Ajie
 Daniel Blumstein
 Richard Coss
 Kathleen Donohue
 Susan Foster
 Andrew Hendry
 Norman Johnson
 David Lahti
 Sally Otto
 Steve Rothstein
 Andy Sih
 Trisha Wittkopp

University of California - Davis
 University of California - Los Angeles
 University of California - Davis
 Harvard University
 Clark University
 McGill University
 University of Massachusetts
 University of Massachusetts
 University of British Columbia
 University of California - Santa Barbara
 University of California - Davis
 University of Michigan

May 15 - 16, 2008

Measuring Evolutionary Change in Modern Human Populations

Coordinators: Diddahally Govindaraju, Andrew Clark, Trudy Mackay, & Stephen Stearns

Participants

Sean Byars
 Douglas Ewbank
 Charles Goodnight
 Diddahally Govindaraju
 Martin Larson
 Trudy Mackay
 Stephen Stearns
 Shamil Sunyaev
 Anatoli Yashin
 Sebastian Zoellner

Yale University
 University of Pennsylvania
 University of Vermont
 Boston University
 Boston University
 North Carolina State University
 Yale University
 University of Michigan
 Duke University
 University of Michigan

May 19 - 22, 2008

Evolutionary Informatics: Supporting Interoperability in Evolutionary Analysis

Coordinators: Arlin Stoltzfus and Rutger Vos

Participants

Brandon Chisham
 Jim Leebens-Mack
 Aaron Mackey
 Enrico Pontelli
 Francisco Prosdocimi
 Weigang Qiu
 Arlin Stoltzfus
 David Swofford
 Rutger Vos
 Xuhua Xia
 Derrick Zwickl

New Mexico State University
 University of Georgia
 GlaxoSmithKline
 New Mexico State University
 University of Louis Pasteur (IGBMC)
 Hunter College
 National Institute of Standards and Technology
 NESCent
 University of British Columbia
 University of Ottawa
 NESCent

May 21 - 23, 2008

Evolution Across the Curriculum

Coordinators: Gordon Uno and Judy Scotchmoor

Participants

Paul Beardsley
 Bruce Boller
 Betty Brown
 Christine Davis
 Adam Fagen
 Pat Gensel
 Roger Harris
 Jay Labov
 Glenn Murphy
 Robert Pennock
 Kristin Savage
 Malcolm Schug
 Judy Scotchmoor
 Amy Sheck
 Gordon Uno
 Jory Weintraub
 Brian Wiegmann

Biological Science Curriculum Study
 Bertie High School
 University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
 Meredith College
 The National Academies
 University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill
 Sigma Xi
 The National Academies
 UK Geneticist/Science communicator/ISE
 University of Michigan
 NESCent
 University of North Carolina, Greensboro
 University of California - Berkeley
 The North Carolina School of Science and Mathematics
 University of Oklahoma
 NESCent
 NESCent

May 27 - 30, 2008

Montane Biodiversity

Coordinators: Catherine Graham, Ken Kozak, and Carsten Rahbek

Participants

Rauri Bowie
 Carlos Daniel Cadena
 Anna Carnaval
 Jon Fjelds
 Catherine Graham
 David Kidd
 Kenneth Kozak
 Christy McCain
 Madhava Meegaskumbura
 Craig Mortiz
 Carsten Rahbek
 Nathan Sanders
 Jeremy VanDerWal
 Kelly Zamudio

University of California - Berkeley
 Universidad de los Andes
 University of California - Berkeley
 University of Copenhagen
 Stony Brook University
 NESCent
 University of Minnesota
 University of Colorado - Boulder
 Harvard University
 University of California - Berkeley
 University of Copenhagen
 University of Tennessee - Knoxville
 James Cook University
 Cornell University

May 28 - 30, 2008

**Synergistic Evolutionary LEarning Consortium:
 Evolution in AcTION**

Coordinators: John Jungck and Anton E. Weosstein

Participants

Sam Donovan
 Kirsten Fisher
 David Hillis
 Kristin Jenkins
 John Jungck
 Stacey Kiser
 Claudia Neuhauser
 Sam Price
 Sue Risseuw
 Katja Schultz
 Jory Weintraub
 Tony Weisstein
 Brian Wiegmann

University of Pittsburgh
 NESCent
 University of Texas - Austin
 NESCent
 BioQUEST Curriculum Consortium
 Lane Community College
 University of Minnesota
 NESCent
 Beloit College
 Tree of Life
 NESCent
 Truman State University
 North Carolina State University

June 9 - 12, 2008

Developing an Integrative Algorithmic Method for Historical Biogeography

Coordinators: Joel Cracraft and Mark Siddall

Participants

Rachel Collin
 Joel Cracraft
 Michael Donoghue
 Frank Fontanella
 Ganesh Ganapathy
 David Kidd
 Wayne Maddison
 Fredrik Ronquist
 Isabel Sanmartin
 Mark Siddall
 David Swofford
 Marcy Uyenoyama
 Derrick Zwickl

Smithsonian Tropical Research Institute
 American Museum of Natural History
 Yale University
 American Museum of Natural History
 NESCent
 NESCent
 University of British Columbia
 Florida State University
 Uppsala University
 American Museum of Natural History
 NESCent
 Duke University
 NESCent

August 22 - 25, 2008

Evolutionary Ecology of Primate Life Histories

Coordinators: Susan Alberts and Karen Strier

Participants

Susan Alberts
 Jeanne Altmann
 Diane Brockman
 Anne Bronikowski
 Marina Cords
 Bill Morris
 Anne Pusey
 Tara Stoinski
 Karen Strier

Duke University
 Princeton University
 University of North Carolina - Charlotte
 Iowa State University
 Columbia University
 Duke University
 University of Minnesota
 Zoo Atlanta and Dian Fossey Gorilla Fund
 University of Wisconsin

October 2-4, 2008

Mathematical Models, Microbes & Evolutionary Diversification

Coordinators: Samantha Forde and Ivana Gudelj

Participants

Martin Ackermann
 Robert Beardmore
 Robert Burch
 Michael Doebeli

Swiss Federal Institute of Technology - Zurich
 Imperial College
 University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
 University of British Columbia

Tom Ferenci	University of Sidney
Samantha Forde	University of California - Santa Cruz
Ivana Gudelj	University of Bath
Christopher Marx	Harvard University
Justin Meyer	Michigan State University
Konstantin Mischaikow	Rutgers University
Olin Silander	Swiss Federal Institute of Technology - Zurich
Hal Smith	Arizona State University
Joshua Weitz	Georgia Institute of Technology

October 9-12, 2008**Modeling Variation in Gene Networks****Coordinators: Paul Magwene and David Houle****Participants**

David Houle	Florida State University
Hao Li	University of California – San Francisco
Paul Magwene	Duke University
Jason Mezey	Cornell University
Jason Moore	Dartmouth College
Patrick Phillips	University of Oregon
Matt Rockman	Princeton University
Mark Siegal	New York University
Joshua Socolar	Duke University
Patricia Wittkopp	University of Michigan

October 26-30, 2008**Phytogeography of the Northern Hemisphere****Coordinators: Michael Donoghue and Paul Manos****Participants**

Michael Donoghue	Yale University
Peter Fritsch	California Academy of Sciences
Jianhua Li	Harvard University
Steven Manchester	Florida Museum of Natural History
Paul Manos	Duke University
Richard Milne	University of Edinburgh
Brian Moore	Yale University
Benjamin Redelings	North Carolina State University
Richard Ree	Field Museum of Natural History
Susanne Renner	University of Munich
Bob Ricklefs	University of Missouri - St. Louis
Stephen Smith	Yale University

Jeffrey Thorne
 Jun Wen
 Jenny Xiang

North Carolina State University
 Smithsonian Institute
 North Carolina State University

October 28 - 30, 2008

**Genetic Monitoring (GeM) Working Group
 Coordinators: Fred Allendorf and Michael Schwartz**

Participants

Fred Allendorf
 C. Scott Baker
 Greg Gregovitch
 Michael Hansen
 Jennifer Jackson
 Katherine Kendall
 Linda Laikre
 Kevin McKelvey
 Brad McRae
 Maile Neel
 Isabelle Olivieri
 Nils Ryman
 Michael Schwartz
 Ruth Shortbull
 Jeffrey Stetz
 David Tallmon
 Christina Vojta
 Donald Waller
 Robin Waples

University of Montana
 Oregon State University
 Southwest Fisheries Science Center
 Technical University of Denmark
 Oregon State University
 US Geological Survey Glacier Field Station
 Stockholm University
 USDA Forest Service
 University of California, Santa Barbara
 University of Maryland
 Universite de Montpellier II
 Stockholm University
 USDA Forest Service
 University of Montana
 University of Montana
 University of Alaska
 US Forest Service
 University of Wisconsin, Madison
 Northwest Fisheries Science Center

NESCent Advisory Meetings

February 6 - 7, 2008

**NESCent Scientific Advisory Board
 Coordinator: Joel Kingsolver**

Participants

Troy Day
 Lisa Donovan
 Fred Gould
 Catherine Graham
 Joel Kingsolver
 William Piel
 Kathleen Smith

Queens University
 University of Georgia
 North Carolina State University
 Stony Brook University
 University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
 Yale University
 NESCent

Jeffrey Todd Strelman
 Paul Turner
 Peter Wagner
 Peter Wainwright
 Marlene Zuk

Georgia Institute of Technology
 Yale University
 Smithsonian Institution
 University of California
 University of California - Riverside

September 11 - 12, 2008

Participants:

Carl Bergstrom
 Julia Clarke
 Michael Donoghue
 Scott Edwards
 Doug Erwin
 Doug Futuyma
 Sergey Gavrilets
 Pat Gensel
 Steve Goff
 Fred Gould
 Joseph Graves, Jr.
 Lou Gross
 Liz Hadly
 Stephanie Hampton
 Jim Hanken
 Brian Hare
 Bryan Heidorn
 David Hillis
 Joel Kingsolver
 Trudy Mackay
 Peter McCartney
 Mark McPeck
 Lisa Nagy
 Rod Page
 Rob Pennock
 Sam Price
 Jonathan Prichard
 Steve Rounsley
 Kathleen Smith
 Maureen Stanton
 David Swofford

NESCent Summit

Coordinator: Kathleen Smith

University of Washington
 North Carolina State University
 Yale University
 Harvard University
 Smithsonian Institution
 State University of New York, Stony Brook
 The University of Tennessee, Knoxville
 University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
 The iPlant Collaborative (iPC)
 North Carolina State University
 North Carolina A&T University
 The University of Tennessee, Knoxville
 Stanford University
 NCEAS
 Harvard University
 Duke University
 National Science Foundation
 University of Texas – Austin
 University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
 North Carolina State University
 National Science Foundation
 Dartmouth College
 University of Arizona
 University of Glasgow
 Michigan State University
 NESCent
 University of Chicago
 The iPlant Collaborative (iPC)
 Duke University
 University of California – Davis
 Duke University

Jeffrey Thorne
Sarah Tishkoff
Saran Twombly
Judy Verbeke
Todd Vision
Peter Wainwright
Marta Wayne
Brian Wiegmann
David Sloan Wilson
Greg Wray

North Carolina State University
University of Pennsylvania
National Science Foundation
National Science Foundation
NESCent
University of California, Davis
University of Florida
North Carolina State University
State University of New York Binghamton University
Duke University

September 12 - 13, 2008

NESCent Senior Advisory Board

Coordinator: Kathleen Smith

Participants

Scott Edwards
Joesph Graves, Jr.
David Hillis
Lisa Nagy
Rod Page
Jonathan Prichard
Kathleen Smith
Maureen Stanton
Sarah Tishkoff

Harvard University
North Carolina A&T University
University of Texas – Austin
University of Arizona
University of Glasgow
University of Chicago
Duke University
University of California – Davis
University of Pennsylvania

Informatics

December 10-14, 2007

Hackathon on Comparative Methods in R

Coordinator: Hilmar Lapp

Participants

David Ackerly
Michael Alfaro
Charles Bell
Ben Bolker
Peter Cowan
Damien de Vienne
Richard Desper
Joe Felsenstein
Luke Harmon

University of California - Berkeley
Washington State University
University of New Orleans
University of Florida
University of California - Berkeley
University of Paris
National Center for Biotechnology Information
University of Washington
University of Idaho

Christoph Heibl	Ludwig-Maximilians Universität, München
Andrew Hipp	Morton Arboretum
Gene Hunt	Smithsonian Institution
Thibaut Jombart	University of Lyon
Steve Kembel	University of California - Berkeley
Aaron King	University of Michigan
Hilmar Lapp	NESCent
Wayne Maddison	University of British Columbia
Peter Midford	University of Kansas
Brian O'Meara	NESCent
David Orme	Imperial College
Emmanuel Paradis	Research Institute for Development
Sam Price	NESCent
Dan Rabosky	Cornell University
Brian Sidlauskas	NESCent
Stacey Smith	Duke University
David Swofford	Duke University
Todd Vision	NESCent
Peter Waddell	University of South Carolina
Amy Zanne	NESCent

Primary Education Evolution Course

July 14 - 18, 2008

**Teaching An Elementary Story of Life
Coordinator: Joseph Fail, Jr.**

Participants

Clemustine Best	Fred Olds Elementary
Cindy Blohm	NESCent
Jean Boller	Windsor Elementary
Joycelyn Bryant	Rashkis Elementary Scholl
Tiffany Clanton	Lawsonville Ave. School
Marion Davis	Forest View Elementary
Joe Fails, Jr.	NESCent
Kathy Joyce	Lawsonville Ave. School
Meg Sauer	Vance Charter School
Amie Tedeschi	Triangle Day School
Maryan Thomas	CI Academy
June Vann	Beaufort Elementary

Phyloinformatics Course**July 24 - August 4, 2008****Participants**

Leonardo Arbiza
 Eszter Ari
 Jim Balhoff
 Bank Beszteri
 Daniela Brites
 Marguerite Butler
 Ivalu Cacho
 Marc Cadotte
 Jason Caravas
 Thomas Clarke
 Mark Cornwell
 Jonathan Davies
 Bhakti Dwivedi
 Jamiel Estill
 Jessica Grant
 Mira Han
 Cristian Hernandez
 Darrin Hulsey
 Stuart Jeffreys
 Todd Jobe
 Zofia Kaliszewska
 Sergei Kosakovsky-Pond
 Hilmar Lapp
 Scott Loarie
 Darrin London
 David Maddison
 Heather Maughan
 Camila Mazzoni
 Michael McKain
 Francois Michonneau
 Kathleen Miglia
 Spencer Muse
 Jeff Oliver
 Brian O'Meara
 José Patané
 Bill Piel
 Ryan Scherle
 Tonia Schwartz

Phyloinformatics Summer Course**Coordinator: Hilmar Lapp**

Prince Felipe Research Centre (CIPF)
 Eötvös Loránd University Budapest
 NESCent
 Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar & Marine Research
 University of Basel, Switzerland
 University of Hawaii
 University of Wisconsin, Madison
 NCEAS
 Wayne State University
 University of North Carolina
 Harvard University
 NCEAS
 University of Dayton
 University of Georgia
 Smith College
 Indiana University Bloomington
 Universidad de Concepcion
 University of Tennessee
 University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill
 University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill
 Harvard University
 University of California, San Diego
 NESCent
 Carnegie Institute, Washington
 Duke University
 University of Arizona
 University of British Columbia
 University College Cork
 University of Georgia, Athens
 University of Florida
 Duke University
 North Carolina State University
 Yale University
 NESCent
 Universidade de São Paulo
 Yale University
 NESCent
 Iowa State University

Stacey Smith	Duke University
Zhiyi Sun	University of Massachusetts, Amherst
James Tarver	University of Bristol
Berit Ullrich	Zoological Research Museum Alexander Koenig
Heroen Verbruggen	Ghent University
Todd Vision	University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill
Oliver Voigt	Courant Research Centre Geobiology, University
Rutger Vos	University of British Columbia
Bastienne Vriesendorp	Ohio State University
Catherine Wagner	Cornell University
James Walters	Cornell University
Laura Wegener Parfrey	University of Massachusetts, Amherst
Dennis Wong	Dalhousie University
Dicky Sick Ki Yu	University of Kentucky
Julia Zichello	The City University of New York Graduate Center

BioQUEST Workshop

May 5-8, 2008

Participants

Jamie Alan	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Christine Davis	Meredith College
Eric Donaldson	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Christian d'Orgeix	Virginia State University
Joao Ferreira	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Emily Fisher	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Trudy Gillevet	Northern Virginia Community College
Gregory Goins	North Carolina A&T State University
Joseph Graves, Jr.	North Carolina A&T State University
Debby Hanmer	University of North Carolina - Pembroke
Randall Hayes	Guilford Technical Community College
Bonnie Kelley	University of North Carolina at Pembroke
Julian Lombardi	Duke University
Lauren McCall	NESCent
Claudia Neuhauser	University of Minnesota
Kathryn Perez	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Morgan Raley	North Carolina Museum of Natural Sciences
James Rose	Carolina Friends School

Synergistic Evolutionary LEarning Consortium Workshop

Coordinators: John Jungck and Anton E. Weosstein

Angela Skeeles-Worley
Shirl Smith
Rebecca Stanley
Douglas Stoner
Kirsten Trowbridge
Anton Weisstein
Sally White

Albemarle High School
Southeast Raleigh Magnet High School
Brunswick County Early College High School
Fayetteville Technical Community College
Bennett College for Women
Truman State University
University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill

Appendix 7

Year 4 Participants Lists – NESCent Other Supported Activities

December 1, 2007 - November 30, 2008

Triangle Working Groups

January 17-18, 2008

Genomic Patterns and Processes of Introgression
Coordinators: Marcy Uyenoyama, Alade Tokuta and Rasmus Nielsen

Participants

David Adeyemi	North Carolina Central University
Yingjun Cao	North Carolina Central University
Sang Chul Choi	North Carolina State University
Andrew Dellinger	Duke University
Ganesh Ganapathy	NESCent
Jody Hey	Rutgers University
Asger Hobolth	North Carolina State University
Yi-Ju Li	Duke Center for Human Genetics
Carlos Machado	University of Arizona
Hao Mei	Duke University
Thomas Mitchell-Olds	Duke University
Richard Morris	University of Miami
Rasmus Nielsen	University of Copenhagen
Mohamed Noor	Duke University
Susan Paulsen	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Susan Paulsen	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Kathryn Perez	Duke University
Benjamin Redelings	North Carolina State University
Laurie Stevison	Duke University
Marcy Uyenoyama	Duke University

May 5-8, 2008

Clockwork: Redefining Interfaces for Molecular Biology and Paleontology
Coordinators: Julia Clarke, Nathalie Nagalingum and Brian Wiegmann

Participants

Jon Auman	NESCent
Matt Bertone	North Carolina State University
Julia Clarke	North Carolina State University
Kristen Dang	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill

Norman Douglas	North Carolina State University
Drew Eddy	North Carolina State University
Ying Fang	University of North Carolina - Wilmington
Olivier Fedrigo	Duke University
Chunmiao Feng	North Carolina State University
Kirsten Fisher	NESCent
Ester Gaya	Duke University
Pat Gensel	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Amanda Grusz	Duke University
Andrii Gryganskyi	Duke University
Yuelong Guo	North Carolina State University
Brendan Hodgkinson	Duke University
Daniel Ksepka	North Carolina State University
Kristin Lamm	North Carolina State University
Mimi Lin	Duke University
Paul Manos	Duke University
John Mercer	Duke University
Jolanta Miadlikowska	Duke University
Kathleen Miglia	Duke University
Nathalie Nagalingum	Harvard University
Michael Nowak	Duke University
Bernadette O'Reilly	Duke University
Kathryn Perez	Duke University
Cristina Isabel Pokorny	Duke University
Sam Price	NESCent
Morgan Raley	N C Museum of Natural Sciences
Benjamin Redelings	North Carolina State University
Hannah Reynolds	Duke University
Rebecca Sealfon	Duke University
Brian Sidlauskas	NESCent
Adam Smith	North Carolina State University
Suja Thomas	University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Jeffrey Thorne	North Carolina State University
Marcy Uyenoyama	Duke University
Marcel van Tuinen	University of North Carolina - Wilmington
David Weisrock	Duke University
Brian Wiegmann	North Carolina State University
Issac Winkler	North Carolina State University
Jenny Xiang	North Carolina State University

Co-Sponsored Meetings**May 13 - 14, 2008****Participants**

Hank Bart
 John Bates
 Stan Blum
 Vanderlei Canhos
 Vishwas Chavan
 Carla Cicero
 Gladys Cotter
 Jim Edwards
 Linda Ford
 Mike Frame
 Rob Guralnick
 Brendan Haley
 James Hanken
 Walter Jetz
 Rick Mayden
 Jim McGuire
 Scott Miller
 Craig Moritz
 Phil Myers
 Town Peterson
 David Reed
 Ryan Scherle
 Carol Spencer
 Peter Uetz
 Dave Vieglais
 David Wake
 Mark Westneat
 John Wiezcorek

Vertebrate Network Meeting**Coordinators: Jim Hanken, Craig Moritz, and David Wake**

Tulane University Museum of Natural History
 The Field Museum
 California Academy of Sciences
 Environmental Information (CRISA), Brazil
 Global Biodiversity Information Facility
 University of California - Berkeley
 U.S. Geological Survey
 Smithsonian Institution
 Harvard University
 U.S. Geological Survey
 University of Colorado
 Harvard University
 Harvard University
 University of California - San Diego
 St. Louis University
 University of California - Berkeley
 Smithsonian Institution
 University of California - Berkeley
 University of Michigan
 University of Kansas
 University of Florida
 NESCent
 University of California - Berkeley
 The J Craig Venter Institute
 University of Kansas
 University of California - Berkeley
 Field Museum of Natural History
 University of California - Berkeley

Appendix 8

Year 4 Participants Lists – Other Meetings Held Not Funded by NESCent December 1, 2007 - November 30, 2008

Hosted Meetings

January 17-18, 2008

**Society for the Study of Evolution
Coordinator: Don Waller**

Participants

Joy Bergelson	University of Chicago
Gisella Caccone	Yale University
Dale Clayton	University of Utah
Troy Day	Queens University
Charles Fenster	University of Maryland
Jessica Gurevitch	Stony Brook University
Jen Mahar	Blackwell Publishing
Mohamed Noor	Duke University
Robert T. Pennock	University of Michigan
Mark Rausher	Duke University
Johanna Schmitt	Brown University
Marjorie Spencer	Blackwell Publishing
Don Waller	University of Wisconsin - Madison

January 18, 2008

**From Beta Taxonomy to DNA Barcoding
Coordinator: Don Stone**

Participants

Jim Hamrick	University of Georgia
Rob Jackson	Duke University
John Kress	Smithsonian Institution
Liz Losos	Organization for Tropical Studies
Paul Manos	Duke University
Thomas Mitchell-Olds	Duke University
Don Stone	Duke University
Greg Wray	Duke University
Gwen Wright	Organization for Tropical Studies

March 19 - 21, 2008

**National Science Foundation Site Visit
Coordinator: National Science Foundation**

Participants

Jim Beach
Jessica Bolker
Carlos Bustamante
Keith Crandall
Michael Cummings
Muriel Poston
Margaret Riley
Susan Singer
Saran Twombly
Bill Zamer

University of Kansas
University of New Hampshire
Cornell University
Brigham Young University, NSF Site Visit Team Chair
University of Maryland
Skidmore College
University of Massachusetts - Amherst
Carleton College
National Science Foundation
National Science Foundation

April 17 - 21, 2008

**Phenoscape Core Meeting and Data Jamboree
Coordinators: Paula Mabee and Todd Vision**

Participants

Jim Balhoff
Miles Coburn
Kevin Conway
Wasila Dahdul
Mário de Pinna
Hilmar Lapp
John Lundberg
Paula Mabee
Peter Midford
Martin Ringwald
Brian Sidlauskas
Todd Vision
Nicole Washington
Monte Westerfield

NESCent
John Carroll University
St. Louis University
Academy of Natural Sciences
Universidade de São Paulo
NESCent
Academy of Natural Sciences
University of South Dakota
University of Kansas
Jackson Laboratories
NESCent
NESCent
University of California - Berkeley
University of Oregon

June 23 - 25, 2008

**Toward an International Exchange Standard or
Vegetation and Biodiversity
Co-occurrence Data
Coordinator: Robert Peet**

Participants

Migue de Cáceras
Martin Kleikamp

Universitat de Barcelona
VegetWeb

Robert Peet
Nick Spencer

University of North Carolina - Chapel Hill
Landcare Research

July 11 - 13, 2008

Participants

Feseha Abebe-Akele
Parker Antin
Burcu Bakir-Gungor
Scott Cain
Dave Clements
Matt Conte
Sean Davey
Victor de Jager
Jason Dzurisin
Ben Faga
Bob Freeman
Jean-Pierre Gauthier
Glenn Harris
Erik F. Y. Hom
Zhiliang Hu
Li Jin
Ed Johnson
Ed Lee
Fabrice Legeai
Xianhua Liu
Prashanti Manda
Tom McNeill
Christos Noutsos
Jason Phillips
Joan Pontius
Sarah Richardson
Stéphanie Sidibe-Bocs
Brett Whitty
Arouna Woukeu
Changjun (Andy) Wu

GMOD Workshop

Coordinator: David Clements

University of New Hampshire
University of Arizona
Medical College of Wisconsin
Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory
NESCent
Howard Hughes Medical Institute
University of Arizona
Radboud University Nijmegen Medical Centre
University of Notre Dame
Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory
Harvard University Medical School
National Institute of Agronomic Research
Virginia State University
Harvard University
Iowa State University
University of Delaware
University of Georgia
Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory
National Institute of Agronomic Research
NESCent
Mississippi State University
Syngenta Biotechnology
University of Chicago
University of North Carolina
National Cancer Institute
Johns Hopkins University
CIRAD
Michigan State University
University of Southampton
Washington State University

Appendix 9a
NESCent Postdoc Data
Applicants and Awards Accepted or Declined - Year 4

Demographics	Postdoc Applicants	Postdoc Awards	Postdoc Acceptances	Postdoc Declines
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Gender

Female	11	4	1	3
Male	14	6	4	2

Residency

USA	22	10	5	5
International	3	0	0	0

Ethnicity

Hispanic	2	1	1	0
Non Hispanic	19	7	4	3
Unknown	2	1	0	1
Do not wish	2	1	0	1

Race

Asian	0	0	0	0
Black	0	0	0	0
Hispanic	0	0	0	0
White	4	2	1	1
Pacific Islander	0	0	0	0
Unknown	21	8	4	4
Do not wish	0	0	0	0

Citizenship

US Citizen	16	7	3	4
International	7	2	2	0
Permanent Res	0	0	0	0
Unknown	2	1	0	1
Do not wish	0	0	0	0

Total Count	25	10	5	5
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Data on NESCent postdocs. All data is self-identification. Country of residence is the home institution of the applicant, and doesn't necessarily reflect citizenship.

Appendix 9b
NESCent Applicant Data for Scholars and Groups - Year 4

Demographics	Sabbatical Scholars	Short-Term Visitors	Scholars Total	Catalysis Meetings	Working Groups	Group Total	Totals
Gender							
Female	1	5	6	4	10	14	20
Male	4	12	16	11	19	30	46
Residency							
USA	5	12	17	10	26	36	53
International	0	5	5	5	3	8	13
Ethnicity							
Hispanic	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
Non Hispanic	2	11	13	7	11	18	31
Unknown	3	3	6	8	18	26	32
Do not wish	0	2	2	0	0	0	2
Race							
Asian	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
Black	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
Hispanic	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
White	1	11	12	3	8	11	23
Pacific Islander	0	0	0	1	0	1	1
Unknown	4	2	6	11	21	32	38
Do not wish	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
Citizenship							
US Citizen	3	11	14	6	15	21	35
International	0	5	6	1	1	2	8
Permanent Res	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Unknown	2	0	2	8	13	21	23
Do not wish	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total Count							
Total Count	5	17	22	15	29	44	66

Demographic data of applicants: Database includes applicants for sabbatical scholars, short-term visitors, and the PIs and Co-PIs of Working Groups and Catalysis Meetings (this database does not capture Ethnicity, Race, or Citizenship for Co-PIs of meeting proposals). Data include applicants from all rounds of proposals for year 4. All demographic data is self-identification. Country of residence is the home institution of the applicant, and doesn't necessarily reflect citizenship.

Appendix 9c
NESCent Award Data for Scholars and Groups - Year 4

Demographics	Sabbatical Scholars	Short-Term Visitors	Scholars Total	Catalysis Meetings	Working Groups	Group Total	Totals
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Gender

Female	1	4	5	4	6	10	15
Male	3	12	15	6	6	12	27

Residency

USA	4	11	15	6	12	18	33
International	0	5	5	4	0	4	9

Ethnicity

Hispanic	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
Non Hispanic	1	10	11	4	4	8	19
Unknown	3	3	6	6	8	14	20
Do not wish	0	2	2	0	0	0	2

Race

Asian	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
Black	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
Hispanic	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
White	1	10	11	2	2	4	15
Pacific Islander			0	0		0	0
Unknown	3	2	5	8	10	18	23
Do not wish	0	1	1	0	0	0	1

Citizenship

US Citizen	2	10	12	4	7	11	23
International	0	5	5	0	0	0	5
Permanent Res	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
Unknown	2	0	2	6	5	11	13
Do not wish	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Total Count	4	16	20	10	12	22	42
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Data on NESCent scientists. All data is self-identification. Group PIs include all Co-PIs. Data include applicants from all rounds of proposals for year 4. All awards for Scholars and Groups were accepted. Data do not include hosted activities.

Appendix 9d

Participant Data
Year 4

	Catalysis Meetings	Working Groups	Advisory	Informatics	Fail Course	Phyloinformatics Course	BioQUEST Workshop	Manage Working Group	Co-sponsored & Hosted	Group Totals
Total Count	67	243	63	29	12	53	25	63	108	663
Gender										
Female	14	79	21	3	11	20	13	30	25	216
Male	52	162	42	25	1	33	10	32	81	438
Gender Unknown	1	2	0	1	0	0	2	1	2	9
Residency										
USA	42	207	60	23	12	39	25	62	96	566
International	25	36	3	6	0	14	0	1	12	97
Race/Ethnicity										
Asian	2	10	0	0	0	5	0	6	6	29
Black	0	2	5	0	6	0	2	0	3	18
Hispanic	9	4	0	1	0	4	1	2	0	21
Native American/Alaskan Native	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2
White	34	148	50	19	4	40	16	29	50	390
Other	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	3
Unknown	21	77	8	9	2	0	6	23	47	193
Do not wish to answer	1	1	0	0	0	3	0	0	2	7

Database includes participants of Working Groups, Catalysis Meetings, and Informatics from Year 4. All demographic data is self-identification. Country of residence is the location of the home institute of the participant, and doesn't necessarily reflect citizenship. Informatics only includes Hackathon. Numbers are not based on unique visits.

Appendix 9e
Home Institution Type
of Funded Participants

Carnegie Classification	# of Unique Visitors
Doctorate-granting Universities	291
International Universities	62
US Research Institutes	39
Master's Colleges and Universities	16
International Research Institutes	14
Special Focus Institutions	14
Government Organizations	11
College Preparatory Schools	8
Elementary Schools	8
US Museums	8
Associate granting Universities	6
Baccalaureate Colleges	5
US Science Academies	4
International Museums	3
Other Organizations	2
International Botanical Gardens	1
US Botanical Gardens	1
US Medical Institutes	0
Total	493

Numbers are based on unique visitors. Data only includes visitors from NESCent funded activities and does not include hosted meetings.

Appendix 9f

Year 4 United States Map

of Visits by Funded Participants
Based on State of Home Institute

State	Total	State	Total	State	Total
Alabama	1	Kansas	4	North Carolina	136
Alaska	1	Kentucky	2	Ohio	2
Arizona	9	Louisiana	3	Oklahoma	1
California	47	Maryland	7	Oregon	4
Colorado	6	Massachusetts	23	Pennsylvania	6
Connecticut	9	Michigan	10	South Carolina	1
Washington DC	8	Minnesota	4	Tennessee	4
Florida	10	Missouri	4	Texas	2
Georgia	9	Montana	5	Utah	6
Hawaii	1	Nebraska	1	Vermont	1
Idaho	2	New Hampshire	2	Virginia	13
Illinois	6	New Jersey	4	Washington	7
Indiana	4	New Mexico	4	Wisconsin	8
Iowa	2	New York	16	Total	395

Note: Numbers are unique visitors. Data only include visitors from NESCent funded activities and does not include hosted meetings.

Year 4 World Map

of Visits by Funded Participants
Based on Country of Home Institute

Country	Total	Country	Total	Country	Total
Argentina	4	Denmark	4	New Zealand	1
Australia	4	France	5	Spain	1
Belgium	1	Germany	11	Sweden	3
Brazil	2	Hungary	1	Switzerland	4
Canada	13	India	1	United Kingdom	11
Chile	8	Ireland	1	United States	395
Colombia	3	Italy	1	<i>Non-US</i>	79
				Totals	474

Note: Numbers are unique visitors. Data only include visitors from NESCent funded activities and does not include hosted meetings.

Year 4 World Map # of Unique Visits by Funded Participants

Years 1-4 United States Map

of Visits by Funded Participants
Based on State of Home Institute

State	Total	State	Total	State	Total
Alabama	2	Louisiana	9	Oklahoma	2
Alaska	2	Maine	2	Oregon	8
Arizona	20	Maryland	21	Pennsylvania	18
California	105	Massachusetts	37	Puerto Rico	4
Colorado	12	Michigan	19	Rhode Island	1
Connecticut	21	Minnesota	9	South Carolina	3
Washington DC	23	Missouri	13	South Dakota	3
Florida	20	Montana	5	Tennessee	5
Georgia	18	Nebraska	3	Texas	13
Hawaii	8	Nevada	2	Utah	9
Idaho	2	New Hampshire	4	Vermont	2
Illinois	25	New Jersey	8	Virginia	19
Indiana	11	New Mexico	7	Washington	15
Iowa	6	New York	50	Wisconsin	8
Kansas	8	North Carolina	266	Wyoming	1
Kentucky	3	Ohio	12	Total	864

Note: Numbers are unique visitors. Data only include visitors from NESCent funded activities and does not include hosted meetings.

Years 1-4 World Map

of Visits by Funded Participants
Based on Country of Home Institute

Country	Total	Country	Total	Country	Total
Argentina	4	France	8	New Zealand	3
Australia	8	Germany	18	Norway	1
Bangladesh	1	Hungary	1	Panama	2
Belgium	1	India	1	Portugal	1
Brazil	4	Ireland	1	Singapore	1
Canada	37	Italy	2	Spain	1
Chile	8	Jamaica	1	Sweden	5
Colombia	3	Japan	6	Switzerland	7
Denmark	7	Madagascar	1	United Kingdom	44
Dominican Republic	2	Mexico	1	United States	864
Finland	1	Netherlands	2	<i>Non-US</i>	<i>183</i>
				Total	1047

Note: Numbers are unique visitors. Data only include visitors from NESCent funded activities and does not include hosted meetings.

Appendix 10
Current NESCent Meetings Expected for Program Year 5
December 1, 2008 - November 30, 2009

Group Leader(s)	Group Type	Meeting Topic
Alberts, Susan Strier, Karen	Work Group	Evolutionary Ecology of Primate Life Histories
Allendorf, Fred Schwartz, Michael	Work Group	Genetic Monitoring (GeM) Working Group
Beall, Christina	Catalysis	Human evolution and adaptation to high-altitude hypoxia
Bergman, Casey Keitman, Martin Dermitzakis, Manolis	Work Group	Synthesizing Computational Resources for Cis-regulatory Molecular Evolution.
Buckley, Lauren Angilletta, Michael Holt, Robert Tewksbury, Joshua	Work Group	NESCent-NCEAS Mechanistic Distribution Models: Energetics, Fitness, and Population Dynamics
Donovan, Sam	Work Group	EOG TREE
Edwards, Erika	Catalysis	Toward a New Synthesis of the Evolutionary History and Ecology of C4 Grasses
Fenster, Charles Armbruster, Scott Diggle, Pamela	Work Group	Floral Assembly: Quantifying the Composition of a Complex Adaptive Structure
Forde, Samantha Gudelj, Ivana	Work Group	Mathematical Models, Microbes & Evolutionary Diversification
Govindaraju, Diddahally Clark, Andrew Mackay, Trudy Stearns, Stephen	Work Group	Measuring Evolutionary Change in Modern Human Populations

Group Leader(s)	Group Type	Meeting Topic
Graham, Catherine Kozak, Ken Rabhbek, Carsten	Work Group	Montane Biodiversity
Hodges, Scott Kramer, Elena Hoekstra, Hopi	Work Group	Building tools for emerging model systems in Development, Evolution, and Ecology
Jenkins, Kristen	Education	Darwin Day
Lahti, David	Work Group	Relaxed Selection and Trait Loss in Evolution
Lapp, Hilmar	Informatics	NESCent Database Interoperability Hackathon
Leebens-Mack, Jim Brenner, Eric	Work Group	The Plant EvoGenetics Working Group: Advancing Comparative Functional Genomics
Magwene, Paul Houle, David	Work Group	Modeling Variation in Gene Networks
Nunn, Charles Hare, Brian	Work Group	How Does Cognition Evolve?
Payne, Jonathan Stempien, Jennifer Kowalewski, Michael	Work Group	Phanerozoic body size trends in time and space: macroevolution and macroecology
Pfennig, David	Work Group	Evolution and Development of Polyphenisms: Pathways to Innovation and Diversification
Richards, Christina Bossdorf, Oliver Pigliucci, Massimo	Catalysis	What Role, if any, Does Heritable Epigenetic Variation Play in Phenotypic Evolution?
Uno, Gordon Scotchmoor, Judy	Work Group	Evolution Across the Curriculum
Wall, Christine	Work Group	Analysis and Synthesis of Physiologic Data from the Mammalian Feeding Apparatus

Appendix # 11

Outreach Activities by NESCent Directors, Staff and Scientists

NESCent Outreach

American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS), Science Communication, Raleigh, NC, Apr-08, Brian Wiegmann, Kristin Jenkins

American Institute of Biological Sciences Annual Meeting (AIBS), Washington, DC, May-08, Kristin Jenkins, booth

AToL, New Orleans, LA, Mar-08, Todd Vision, Brian Wiegmann, presented paper, poster and booth

BioPharmaceutical Technology Center Institute (BTCD), Bioethics Forum, Washington, DC, May-08, Kristin Jenkins,

BioQUEST 2008, St Louis, MI, Jun-08, Kristin Jenkins, teacher workshop

Education Summit, Washington, DC, May-08, Brian Wiegmann, Kristin Jenkins

Intelligent Systems for Molecular Biology Conference 2008 (ISMB 2008), Toronto, ON, Canada, Jul-08, Todd Vision, Hilmar Lapp, presented paper and poster

iPlant, Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory, NY, Apr-08, Todd Vision, served on panel discussion

National Association of Biology Teachers, Memphis, TN, Oct-08, Brian Wiegmann, Jory Weintraub, presented paper and booth

National Science Teachers Association / North Carolina Science Teachers Association, Charlotte, NC, Oct-08, Jory Weintraub, Kristin Jenkins, presented paper and booth

North Carolina Science Blogging, Research Triangle Park, NC, Jan-08, Kristin Jenkins

Salmon Evolution Workshop, National Marine Fisheries service, Dec-08, Joel Kingsolver, presentation on NESCent activities and opportunities

Society for Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans in Science (SACNAS), Salt Lake City, UT, Oct-08, Jory Weintraub, Brian Sidlauskas, Paula Spaeth, presented paper and booth

Society for Integrative and Comparative Biology, San Antonio, TX, Jan-08, Jory Weintraub, booth

Society for the Study of Evolution, Evolution 2008, Minneapolis, MN, Jun-08, Kathleen Smith, Joel Kingsolver, Todd Vision, Brian Wiegmann, Kristin Jenkins, Hilmar Lapp, Jory Weintraub, Jim Balhoff, Brian O'Meara, presented paper, poster and booth

Other Meetings and Collaborations

Annual Meeting of Society of Integrative and Comparative Biologists, San Antonio, TX, Jan-08, Brian Sidlauskas, presented paper

Annual Meeting of the American Society of Ichthyologists and Herpetologists, Montreal, Canada, Jul-08, Brian Sidlauskas, presented paper

BioHackathon 2008, Tokyo, Japan, Feb-08, Hilmar Lapp, worked in the BioSQL and PhyloWS subgroups

Bioinformatics Open Source Conference (BOSC) in the 16th Annual International Conference Intelligent Systems for Molecular Biology, Toronto, Canada, Jul-08, Hilmar Lapp, Jim Balhoff, Xianhua Liu, co-organizer, presented paper

Bio-Ontologies 2008, Toronto, Canada, Jul-08, Balhoff

Bodega Bay Workshop in Applied Phylogenetics, Bodega Bay, CA, Mar-08, Brian O'Meara, taught workshop

DataNetONE site-visit by NSF, Albuquerque, NM, May-08, Hilmar Lapp

33rd International Geological Congress, Oslo, Norway, Aug-08, Paula Spaeth

Interface 2008, Durham, NC, May-08, Brian O'Meara, presented paper

INTEROP research coordination meeting, Albuquerque, NM, Sep-08, Hilmar Lapp

iPlant Grand Challenge Workshop, Biosphere II, AZ, Nov-08, Todd Vision, presented paper

Morphbank Ontology workshop, Tallahassee, FL, May-08, Jim Balhoff

Open Science Grid Workshop & Training, Chapel Hill, NC, Mar-08, Hilmar Lapp

Phenoscape Data Jamboree 1 and Project Meeting, NESCent, Apr-08, Todd Vision, Hilmar Lapp, Jim Balhoff

Phenoscape Data Jamboree 2 and Project Meeting, Rapid City, SD, Sep-08, Todd Vision, Hilmar Lapp, Jim Balhoff

Phyloinformatics Workshop, Edinburgh, UK, Oct-08, Hilmar Lapp

Presenting Data and Information: A One-Day Course by Edward Tufte, Morrisville, NC, Mar-08, Hilmar Lapp

SEEK research coordination meeting, Albuquerque, NM, Sep-08, Ryan Scherle

Society for Integrative and Comparative Biology, San Antonio, TX, Jan-08, Brian O'Meara, presented paper

TDWG Annual Meeting, Perth, Australia, Oct-08, Hilmar Lapp, presented paper

The Biology of Genomes, Cold Spring Harbor, NY, May-08, Einat Hazkani-Covo, presented poster

TraitNet RCN meeting, New York City, NY, Dec-07, Hilmar Lapp

Appendix 12

NESCent Call for Proposals

Announcement Sent to the Following Web Site sand List Serves

1. American Ornithological Union (AOU)
2. American Physiological Society – Comparative & Evolutionary Physiology Section (APS – CEPS)
3. American Society of Ichthyologists and Herpetologists (ASIH)
4. American Society of Mammalogists (ASM)
 - a. Journal On-line
 - b. Web Site
5. Animal Behavior Society (ABS)
6. BIRDNET web site
7. Botanical Society of America (BSA)
8. EvolDir - Evolution Directory (EvolDir)
9. Evolution and Medicine web site
10. Genetics Society of America (GSA)
11. Geological Society of America
12. Paleobotany list serve (through Pat Gensel)
13. Paleontological Society web site
14. Society of Developmental Biology (SDB)
15. Society for Integrative & Comparative Biology (SICB)
16. Society of Molecular Biology and Evolution (SMBE)
17. Society for Study of Evolution (SSE)
 - a. Journal On-line
 - b. Web Site
18. Society of Systematic Biology (SSB)
19. Society for Vertebrate Paleontology (SVP)

Appendix 13
NESCent Student Interns
Year4 - 2007-2008

Last Name	First Name	Project	Mentor
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Undergraduate Student Interns

Duke University

Bullock	Allison	Ecological and morphological diversification of characiform fishes	Sidlauskas
Chen	Siyang	Recent non-repetitive insertions in the human genome	Covo-Hazkani
Gillis	Tiffany	Development of NESCent statistical data for NSF reporting	Wilson
Haigler	Laura	Development of NESCent statistical data for NSF reporting	Sturkey
Hardie	Frances	Woody Plant Evolutionary Anatomy and Ecology: Collecting data on parenchyma and fiber distribution in xylem sapwood	Zanne
Jackson-Ricketts	Justine	The relationship between swimming speeds, diving capabilities and dietary strategies in whales and dolphins	Price
Kilgore	Rosie	Data importation into the Dryad repository	Scherle
Schmidt	Jacob	Database on fossil cetaceans, to record age, taxonomy and most importantly size	Price
Zeller	Ray	Estimating the number of numts in fully sequenced genomes	Covo-Hazkani
Zheng	Perry	A sample-based approach to estimating character-specific diversification rates	Ganapathy

North Carolina State University

Bosnjak	Diane	Website development/maintenance, database research	EOG
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University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Dyer	Rebecca	Development of NESCent statistical data for NSF reporting	Henry
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**NESCent Student Interns
Year4 - 2007-2008**

Last Name	First Name	Project	Mentor
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Graduate Student Interns

Duke University

Debroy	Nihshanka	Development and implementation of statistical models to test the effects of geography on species diversification	Ganapathy
Halappanavar	Amrita	Ancestral population genomics with an explicit model of the coalescent with recombination	Ganapathy

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Bapat	Amol	Development of the Dryad repository interface and system architecture.	Scherle
Carrier	Sarah	Qualitative study of NESCent products	Vision
Diamond	Sarah	Development of NESCent science and synthesis products relating to awards	Kingsolver
Thompson	Abbey	Evolutionary biologists attitudes and behaviors on data sharing	Greenberg
White	Holly	Development of Dryad, a digital data repository - Data attitudes and behavior survey	Greenberg

Interns Who Recently Completed Bachelors Degree

Duke University

Balaban	Alexandra	A sample-based approach to estimating character-specific diversification rates	Ganapathy
Blohm	Cynthia	Development of evolution curriculum for elementary students	Fail

African American students shown in bold.

Appendix 14

NESCent Web Site Information

Total Visitors from September 1, 2007 to August 31, 2008: 42,488

■ New Visitor	21,419	50.41%
■ Returning Visitor	21,069	49.59%

Daily Average: 116 Visits/Day

Weekly Average: 817 Visits/Week

Visitor Home Location

North Carolina (including internal): 16,794

United States (non-North Carolina): 17,447

International: 8,247

Most Frequently Visited Pages:

Education and Outreach Home

Science and Synthesis Home

About NESCent

Awards Page

Informatics

NESCent Monthly Web Site Traffic - NC and Other

Month	North Carolina	Other	Total
September 07	1,107	1,472	2,579
October 07	1,450	2,387	3,837
November 07	1,137	2,165	3,302
December 07	925	1,636	2,561
January 08	2,002	1,862	3,864
February 08	1,479	2,041	3,520
March 08	1,711	2,650	4,361
April 08	1,751	2,965	4,716
May 08	1,599	2,623	4,222
June 08	1,097	1,989	3,086
July 08	1,324	1,844	3,168
August 08	1,212	2,060	3,272
All	16,794	25,694	42,488

Appendix 15 NESCent Staff Chart

